

Supplementary Materials

Benchmarking of Sequence-to-Graph Alignment Tools with Parameter Tuning

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INTRODUCTION

This supplementary document includes additional figures referenced in the main manuscript. These figures present extended evaluation results across all datasets and parameter settings used in our benchmarking study.

C4 FIGURES

A. GedMap - Short Read

Fig. 1: C4 Dataset – Similarity at $d = 2$

Fig. 2: C4 Dataset – Similarity at $d = 6$

Fig. 3: C4 Dataset – Similarity at $d = 10$

Fig. 4: C4 Dataset – Memory usage $d = 6$

Fig. 5: C4 Dataset – Time usage $d = 10$

B. GedMap - Long Read

Fig. 6: C4 Dataset – Similarity at $d = 2$

Fig. 7: C4 Dataset – Similarity at $d = 6$

Fig. 8: C4 Dataset – Similarity at $d = 10$

Fig. 9: C4 Dataset – Memory usage $d = 6$

Fig. 10: C4 Dataset – Time usage $d = 10$

C. Graph Aligner - Short Read

Fig. 11: C4 Dataset – Similarity at $d = 2$

Fig. 12: C4 Dataset – Similarity at $d = 6$

Fig. 15: C4 Dataset – Time usage $d = 10$

D. Graph Aligner - Long Read

Fig. 13: C4 Dataset – Similarity at $d = 10$

Fig. 16: C4 Dataset – Similarity at $d = 2$

Fig. 14: C4 Dataset – Memory usage $d = 6$

Fig. 17: C4 Dataset – Similarity at $d = 6$

MHC FIGURES

E. GedMap - Short Read

Fig. 18: C4 Dataset – Similarity at $d = 10$

Fig. 21: MHC Dataset – Similarity at $d = 2$

Fig. 19: C4 Dataset – Memory usage $d = 6$

Fig. 22: MHC Dataset – Similarity at $d = 6$

Fig. 20: C4 Dataset – Time usage $d = 10$

Fig. 23: MHC Dataset – Similarity at $d = 10$

Fig. 24: MHC Dataset – Memory usage $d = 6$

Fig. 27: MHC Dataset – Similarity at $d = 6$

Fig. 25: MHC Dataset – Time usage $d = 10$

Fig. 28: MHC Dataset – Similarity at $d = 10$

F. GedMap - Long Read

Fig. 26: MHC Dataset – Similarity at $d = 2$

Fig. 29: MHC Dataset – Memory usage $d = 6$

Fig. 30: MHC Dataset – Time usage $d = 10$

Fig. 33: MHC Dataset – Similarity at $d = 10$

G. Graph Aligner - Short Read

Fig. 31: MHC Dataset – Similarity at $d = 2$

Fig. 34: MHC Dataset – Memory usage $d = 6$

Fig. 32: MHC Dataset – Similarity at $d = 6$

Fig. 35: MHC Dataset – Time usage $d = 10$

H. Graph Aligner - Long Read

Fig. 36: MHC Dataset – Similarity at $d = 2$

Fig. 37: MHC Dataset – Similarity at $d = 6$

Fig. 38: MHC Dataset – Similarity at $d = 10$

Fig. 39: MHC Dataset – Memory usage $d = 6$

Fig. 40: MHC Dataset – Time usage $d = 10$

YEAST FIGURES

I. GedMap - Short Read

Fig. 41: yeast Dataset – Similarity at $d = 2$

Fig. 42: yeast Dataset – Similarity at $d = 6$

Fig. 45: yeast Dataset – Time usage $d = 10$

J. GedMap - Long Read

Fig. 43: yeast Dataset – Similarity at $d = 10$

Fig. 46: yeast Dataset – Similarity at $d = 2$

Fig. 44: yeast Dataset – Memory usage $d = 6$

Fig. 47: yeast Dataset – Similarity at $d = 6$

K. Graph Aligner - Short Read

Fig. 48: yeast Dataset – Similarity at $d = 10$

Fig. 51: yeast Dataset – Similarity at $d = 2$

Fig. 49: yeast Dataset – Memory usage $d = 6$

Fig. 52: yeast Dataset – Similarity at $d = 6$

Fig. 50: yeast Dataset – Time usage $d = 10$

Fig. 53: yeast Dataset – Similarity at $d = 10$

Fig. 54: yeast Dataset – Memory usage $d = 6$

Fig. 57: yeast Dataset – Similarity at $d = 6$

Fig. 55: yeast Dataset – Time usage $d = 10$

Fig. 58: yeast Dataset – Similarity at $d = 10$

L. Graph Aligner - Long Read

Fig. 56: yeast Dataset – Similarity at $d = 2$

Fig. 59: yeast Dataset – Memory usage $d = 6$

Fig. 60: yeast Dataset – Time usage $d = 10$